

Sand smelt larvae's resilience to hypoxia and implications for thermal tolerance

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Hypoxia did not alter weight, total length and body condition.
- A metabolic depression was observed in conditions of reduced oxygen availability.
- Hypoxia reduced thermal tolerance.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Deoxygenation is a growing threat to marine ecosystems, with an increase in the frequency, extent and intensity of hypoxia events in recent decades. These phenomena will pose various challenges to marine species, as it affects their survival, growth, body condition, metabolism and ability to handle other environmental stressors, such as temperature. Early life stages are particularly vulnerable to these changes. Thus, it is crucial to understand how these initial phases will respond to hypoxia to predict the impacts on marine populations and ecosystems. In this work, we aimed to evaluate the effect of oxygen (O_2) availability on fitness related traits (mortality, growth and body condition), metabolism (Routine metabolic rates [RMR]) and thermal tolerance (CTmax), in early stages of *Atherina presbyter*, exposed for two weeks, to two O_2 levels: normoxia ($6.5-7.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and hypoxia ($2-2.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), through an experiment setup. Our findings showed that while low oxygen levels did not negatively impact mortality, total length, weight, or body condition (Fulton K), the larvae undergo metabolic depression when exposed to hypoxia, as an energy conservation mechanism. Furthermore, CTmax suffered a significant reduction in low O_2 availability, due to the inability of the circulatory and respiratory systems to fulfill energy demands.

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These outcomes suggest that although early life stages of *Atherina presbyter* can survive under low oxygen environments, they are less capable of dealing with sudden increases in temperature when oxygen is scarce.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, a combination of factors including rising ocean temperatures, increased water column stratification and eutrophication has led to a concerning 2 % decline in global dissolved oxygen (O_2) levels (Schmidtke et al., 2017; Limburg et al., 2020). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) projects that ocean temperatures may rise by 1–4 °C, depending on the shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP) scenario, consequently declining oceanic O_2 levels by ~7 % by the end of the century (IPCC, 2022). Moreover, longer and lasting episodes of coastal eutrophication are exacerbating the frequency, extent and duration of hypoxia events (Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008; Zhang et al., 2010; Limburg et al., 2020). Breitburg et al. (2018) points out that O_2 minimum zones have increased by 4.5 million km^2 and >700 coastal regions have O_2 levels below 2 $mg\ L^{-1}$ (Breitburg et al., 2018).

Assessments of hypoxia's impact on fish consistently reveal detrimental effects on condition (Casini et al., 2016; Cottingham et al., 2018; Müller et al., 2023), growth (Vanderplancke et al., 2015; Obirikorang et al., 2020; Aksakal and Ekinci, 2021), metabolism (Mattiasen et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2023) and physiology (Motyka et al., 2017; Mignucci et al., 2021; Lima et al., 2024a). *Gadus morhua* experienced increased mortality and sub-lethal effects even at O_2 concentrations exceeding 2 $mg\ L^{-1}$ (Vaquer-Sunyer and Duarte, 2008). Hypoxia reduced growth in *Morone saxatilis* (Brandt et al., 2009) and body mass in *Salmo salar* (Remen et al., 2013). *Sebastes caurinus* and *S. mystinus* exhibited a decrease in maximum metabolic rates and aerobic scope when exposed to O_2 concentrations of 2 $mg\ L^{-1}$ (Mattiasen et al., 2020). Reduced routine metabolic rates [RMR (aerobic metabolism)] were also observed in *Scophthalmus maximus* and *Dicentrarchus labrax* when exposed to O_2 concentrations of 3.5 $mg\ L^{-1}$ (Chabot and Dutil, 1999; Pichavant et al., 2000). Several studies have suggested a relationship between hypoxia and thermal tolerance (Ellis et al., 2013; Zanuzzo et al., 2019), which is explored through the oxygen- and capacity-limited thermal tolerance (OCLTT) hypothesis (Pörtner and Knust, 2007; Pörtner, 2010). Briefly, this hypothesis proposes that with increasing temperature, the supply of O_2 to tissues may be impaired if energetic metabolic demands surpass the respiratory and circulatory capacities of fishes (Pörtner, 2010). As such, the upper thermal limit of water-breathing fishes is highly sensitive to O_2 availability (McDonnell et al., 2019). In this sense, one of the most widely used methodologies for the study of thermal tolerance is the critical thermal maximum (CTmax), the highest temperature at which a fish exhibits loss of equilibrium after acute thermal exposure (Morgan et al., 2018), indicative of the collapse of life-essential physiological functions (McDonnell et al., 2019). On this matter, reduced CTmax has been observed when marine fishes are exposed to hypoxia. Adults of *Chromis atripectoralis*, *Cheilodipterus quinquelineatus* and *Acanthochromis polyacanthus*, displayed a decrease in CTmax when subjected to O_2 concentrations of 30 % (Ern et al., 2017) and *Gadus morhua* to mild hypoxia conditions (Zanuzzo et al., 2019).

Fish may respond to hypoxia through behavioral and physiological adjustments (Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2019; Mattiasen et al., 2020). While some may move to more suitable areas to preserve habitat niche under normoxic conditions (LaBone et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2023), others may reduce swimming and foraging activities to preserve energy (Chabot and Claireaux, 2008; French and Wahl, 2018). Otherwise, fish may attempt to maintain blood O_2 levels through increased ventilation and increased circulatory capacity (Mattiasen et al., 2020) or reduce metabolic rates (Dupont-Prinet et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2021) to conserve energy. However, escape responses and acclimation may prove ineffective under severe and prolonged hypoxia. In such scenarios, fish metabolism is likely to switch from aerobic to anaerobic to meet energetic demands

(Lima et al., 2024a).

To date, most studies have focused on the effects of hypoxia on juveniles and adults (Islam et al., 2020; Aksakal and Ekinci, 2021; Negrete Jr et al., 2022), and there is a lack of knowledge about the effects of hypoxia on early stages (Bardon-Albaret and Saillant, 2016; Cadiz et al., 2018), especially on fitness and metabolism (Lima et al., 2024a, 2024b). Studying the effects of hypoxia is particularly important during the early life stages of fish, since changes in life history strategies can lead to unsuccessful recruitment to adult populations (Cadiz et al., 2018; Del Rio et al., 2019). This vulnerable stage does not have fully developed regulatory systems to maintain homeostasis, making it particularly sensitive to environmental changes (Bromhead et al., 2015).

To address this concern, we used early stages of the sand-smelt, *Atherina presbyter*, as a model species. This is an inshore species, which is occasionally found in estuarine regions and lagoons (Francisco et al., 2009). It inhabits the Mediterranean and the northeast Atlantic, from the Canary Islands to the British Isles (Froese and Pauly, 2023), although it is found sporadically in the Azores archipelago (Santos et al., 1997). Spawning occurs in shallow waters and larvae develop in the nearshore (Francisco et al., 2009; Vicente and Faria, 2021). To that end, in the present study we assessed whether fitness-related traits (i.e. growth and Fulton's condition), Routine Metabolic Rates and CTmax in the early stages of the *Atherina presbyter* are affected by chronic exposure to hypoxia (2–2.5 $O_2\ mg\ L^{-1}$) when compared to optimal conditions (>7 $O_2\ mg\ L^{-1}$). This is of particular relevance because the habitat of this species (Atlantic and Mediterranean) is often subject to extreme events, such as hypoxia (Breitburg et al., 2018) and marine heat waves (Galli et al., 2017; Plecha et al., 2021), which are expected to be intensified by the advance of climate change (Galli et al., 2017). We anticipate that growth and condition will be negatively impacted by hypoxia due to decreased food intake (Zambonino-Infante et al., 2017), RMR will be reduced as an energy conservation strategy (Pichavant et al., 2001; Farrell and Richards, 2009), and CTmax is expected to decrease due to insufficient O_2 supply to tissues (Islam et al., 2020; Leeuwis et al., 2021).

2. Methods

2.1. Fish rearing and experimental setup

Fish larvae were collected nearshore at Professor Luiz Saldanha Marine Park (Sesimbra, 38° 28' N; 8° 59' W) in October 2023, using dip nets, and immediately transported to the fish facilities of ISPA-Instituto Universitário in containers with controlled temperature and aeration. On arrival, larvae (post-flexion stage) were placed in a 240 L tank for quarantine for 7 days to recover from handling stress and transport, and acclimatize to the new environment (Lima et al., 2024b), and kept under similar conditions as the ones found in their natural environment at the time of capture [salinity (35 PSU), temperature (20 °C) and photoperiod (14 L:10D)]. The tank was equipped with protein skimmer, and biological and mechanical filtration, and enriched with artificial algae. During this period, fish were fed twice a day with live *Artemia*.

Thereafter, larvae were transferred to 30 L tanks, at a density of 20–22 individuals per tank, with temperature, salinity and photoperiod matching the conditions from the quarantine tank. The temperature of 20 °C was established on the basis of the average sea surface temperature recorded in the Arrábida region during the fall season (when the fish were collected) over the last three decades, according to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). After 5 days of acclimation (Feidantsis et al., 2009; Madeira et al., 2016a), the tanks were assigned to one of two treatments, each with two replicates: 1) normoxia 6.5–7.2 $mg\ L^{-1}\ O_2$ (90–100 % DO) and 2) hypoxia 2–2.5 mg

$L^{-1} O_2$ (27–34 % DO).

The hypoxia value simulates the conditions of the coastal dead zones found along the geographic distribution of the species (Breitburg et al., 2018). In the hypoxia treatment, O_2 levels were decreased at a rate of $\sim 1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ day over 5 days, until reach the desired level of $2\text{--}2.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, by injecting pure nitrogen into the tanks with the aid of solenoid valves and an Oxygen Regulator Computer (Loligo systems OXY-REG). In the normoxia treatment, O_2 levels were maintained through aeration stones. Larvae were exposed for 2 weeks to the different treatments. During this period, larvae were fed twice a day with live *Artemia*. Oxygen availability, salinity and temperature were checked daily using a multiparameter probe (HI98194, Hanna Instruments), while other water quality

parameters such as ammonia and nitrites were analyzed twice a week and kept below critical levels (ammonia- $< 0.1 \text{ mg/L}$; nitrites- $< 1 \text{ mg/L}$). Routine Metabolic Rates and CTmax were analyzed after 2 weeks of exposure. After the trials, the fish were euthanized with an overdose of M222, weighed, measured (total and standard length) and the Fulton Condition K was calculated using the following formula:

$$K = 100 * (\text{Weight} / \text{Length}^3)$$

2.2. Routine metabolic rates (RMR)

Oxygen consumption rate (MO_2) was determined using an

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of the intermittent flow system. (1) Pump, which will move the water to the refrigerator and the UV in order to sterilize it; (2) flush pump, which will move the water to the respirometry chambers during the flush periods; (3) air stone; (4) N_2 stone; (5) respirometry chambers; (6) non-return valve, which will prevent the water from returning to the chambers; (7) peristaltic pump, will promote the homogenization of water inside the chambers; and (8) sensor spot.

intermittent-flow respirometry method, as described by Svendsen et al. (2016). The experimental trials followed the guidelines for reporting methods in aquatic intermittent-flow respirometry as outlined by Killen et al. (2021) (refer to Supplemental Table S1 for details). Respirometry trials were performed between 7:30 and 18:00 h, with two trials conducted each day. Each trial involved the simultaneous operation of eight respirometry chambers, with half designated for normoxia conditions and the remainder for hypoxia. Out of these eight chambers, six were dedicated to measuring fish oxygen consumption, while the remaining were used for background respiration assessment (i.e. only water in the chamber). A total of 12 fish were used for each treatment, encompassing two days of respirometry trials, comprising a total of four runs. Fish were not fed in the 24 h before the trial to ensure a post-absorptive state.

Each fish (0.068 ± 0.023 g) was individually placed in an acrylic vacuum sealed respirometry chamber, with a total volume of 60 mL (50 mL empty chamber and 10 mL of tubing), which was submerged in a 55 L water bath with the same temperature employed throughout the experiment (20 °C). After being placed inside the chamber, the fish was left to acclimate for one hour. In order to reduce activity levels associated with interaction between individuals and external disturbances, the chambers were covered with opaque tape. Following the acclimation period, oxygen consumption was measured for 2 h, in three 35 min cycles, each consisting of a 23 min of measurement period (closed phase), 7 min of waiting period and 5 min of flush. The duration of each cycle was determined through a preliminary assay to ensure that O₂ levels did not drop >20 % in the normoxia treatment (i.e. below 80 % O₂ saturation) and 10 % in the hypoxia treatment (i.e. below 17 % O₂ saturation), and that the flush period was long enough to replenish the O₂ at the desired level (Lima et al., 2024a).

Between each cycle, an automated flush pump, submerged in a 120 L reservoir, with water matching temperature, salinity and oxygen levels of those in the original treatment, supplied and renewed the four chambers of each respirometry set with clean seawater, at a rate of 32 mL/min/chamber (Fig. 1). These pumps were controlled via a Profilux controlling system (Profilux4, GHL, Germany), with a programmed timing sequence regulated by the GHL Control Center Software (version 1.1.4.4). Temperature inside the reservoirs was maintained through refrigerators. The O₂ level in the normoxia reservoir was maintained via O₂ aeration stones, while in the hypoxia reservoir it was maintained at 2.5 mg L^{-1} by injecting pure nitrogen with the aid of a solenoid valve and an Oxygen Regulator Computer (Loligo systems OXY-REG). Each reservoir was equipped with a UV light for water sterilization, thereby diminishing bacterial respiration.

To ensure water mixture within each chamber throughout the measurement periods, each chamber was connected to a peristaltic pump that enabled water circulation within the chamber through an external closed loop of gas-tight tubing, maintaining a flow rate of 2 mL/min.

The oxygen consumption was measured by an O₂ sensor spot (OXSP5, Pyroscience, Germany) placed inside each chamber, which was connected to a FireSting Optical Oxygen Meter (FireSting-O2-4C, Pyroscience, Germany) via fiber-optic cables (SPFIB-LNS, Pyroscience, Germany). Each run lasted 2 h, totalizing 3 records of O₂ consumption per fish, which were used as replicates in the MO₂ analysis. During the run, the O₂ intake was also analyzed in a water-only chamber to determine the background respiration. The chamber chosen to analyze background respiration was changed between runs. Before each run sensors were calibrated, and chambers cleaned with distilled water and 70 % ethanol before being refilled with seawater.

Routine metabolic rate was determined by the mean MO₂ using the respR package in rstudio (version 4.2.2). Only MO₂ values with an R² equal to or >0.9 were considered. The RMR was expressed in milligram of oxygen per kilogram per hour.

2.3. Critical thermal maximum (CTmax)

For the analysis of CTmax, 20 larvae from normoxia treatment and 16 larvae from hypoxia treatment (0.080 ± 0.028 g) were exposed to a constant water temperature increase until reaching the temperature at which they exhibited loss of equilibrium (LOE). Larvae were not fed in the 24 h prior to trials and on the day of treatment they were transferred to two 5 L tanks, one for the hypoxia treatment and one for the normoxia treatment. The O₂ levels were maintained at the established thresholds by bubbling compressed air via aeration stones for the normoxia exposed larvae, or by injecting pure nitrogen with the aid of a solenoid valve and an Oxygen Regulator Computer (Loligo systems OXY-REG) into the tanks for the hypoxia exposed larvae. The tanks were inside a regulated water bath, which was connected to a heater circulator (Multitemp III, Pharmacia Biotech). O₂ levels and temperature were constantly monitored throughout the trials using a multiparameter probe (H198194, Hanna instruments).

After a 2-h of acclimation period, the temperature was increased at a rate of 1 °C per hour until the fish exhibited LOE (Madeira et al., 2016b), typically identified by the occurrence of one or more of the following behaviors: 1) lateral buoyancy, 2) lethargy, 3) start of backwards swimming and 4) vertical position with the snout to the bottom of the tank. Upon reaching LOE the temperature was registered for each fish, following which they were transferred to a recovery tank to assess survival rates in the subsequent 24 h.

2.4. Data analysis

The data normality was tested through the Shapiro Wilk test and confirmed through the residual's plots, while the homogeneity of variances was analyzed through the Bartlett test. Due to limited replication, we used mixed model using tanks as random factors to control the likelihood of significant differences being found. The total length followed a normal distribution and was analyzed through a linear mixed effect models ("lmerTest" package in R) with the treatment as a fixed factor and the tank as a random factor. The weight, Fulton's condition k, CTmax and RMR were analyzed through a Gamma distribution [variance $V(\mu_i) = \mu_i^2/\nu$], and a logarithmic-link $\log(\mu)$ using Generalized linear mixed model (GLMM, "glmmTMB" package in R). Each tank was used as a nested random repeated factor within the main effects to reduce the chances of a type I error. The goodness-of-fit of each model was checked using the package DHARMA. All statistical analysis was developed in R statistics, Rstudio (Version 4.2.2). Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.), and *p* values below 0.05 were considered significant.

3. Results

Throughout the two weeks of exposure, no mortality was observed in either of the treatments. Exposure to hypoxia did not affect growth in total length and weight ($p = 0.276$), with total length and weight averaging 2.42 ± 0.27 cm and 0.07 ± 0.02 g for fish kept under normoxia, and 2.50 ± 0.31 cm and 0.09 ± 0.03 g for fish under hypoxia (Fig. 2A and B). Similarly, hypoxia did not induce changes on Fulton's condition K ($p = 0.951$), with a K value of 0.53 ± 0.08 observed under normoxia and 0.52 ± 0.07 under hypoxia (Fig. 2C).

Exposure to hypoxia significantly reduced RMR ($p < 0.001$) by ~ 2.4 -fold, with values ranging from 317.58 ± 164.25 mg/kg/h to 128.53 ± 48.98 mg/kg/h, in normoxia and hypoxia treatments, respectively (Fig. 3A). Additionally, CTmax in fishes exposed to hypoxia (29.42 ± 2.34 °C) was significantly reduced ($p < 0.001$) by ~ 1.17 fold when compared to those exposed to normoxia (34.54 ± 1.39 °C) (Fig. 3B).

4. Discussion

Coastal hypoxic habitats have become more frequent in marine

Fig. 2. A) Total length, B) Weight and C) Fulton's condition K of *Atherina presbyter* exposed to normoxia (6.5–7.2 mg/L, N = 34) and hypoxia (2.0–2.5 mg/L, N = 29) conditions for a two-week period. In the boxplot the error bars represent the upper and lower limits of the data, the bottom and top of the boxplot are the 1st and 3rd quartiles, the line inside the box is the median, and any outliers are shown as black circles.

ecosystems in recent decades and may pose a threat to species that use nearshore habitats as breeding grounds (Breitburg et al., 2018; Limburg et al., 2020), such as *A. presbyter*. However, the effects of oxygen depletion on the fitness and physiology of fish early stages are not yet fully understood. Our results show that hypoxia does not induce changes in body condition of *A. presbyter* early life stages, which is in line with the results obtained in *Diplodus sargus* larvae (Lima et al., 2024a), but contrasts with those obtained for *Dicentrarchus labrax* larvae (Vanderplancke et al., 2015; Cadiz et al., 2018), juveniles of *Scophthalmus maximus* (Pichavant et al., 2000, 2001) and *D. labrax* (Pichavant et al.,

Fig. 3. A) Routine Metabolic Rates (normoxia N = 12; hypoxia N = 12) and B) CTmax (normoxia N = 20; hypoxia N = 16) of *Atherina presbyter* exposed to normoxia (6.5–7.2 mg/L) and hypoxia (2.0–2.5 mg/L) conditions. Bold asterisks (*) represent significant differences between treatments. In the boxplot the error bars represent the upper and lower limits of the data, the bottom and top of the boxplot are the 1st and 3rd quartiles, the line inside the box is the median, and any outliers are shown as black circles.

2001). Likewise, hypoxia did not induce effects on length, which contradicts the results observed in *Diplodus sargus* (Lima et al., 2024a) and *Dicentrarchus labrax* larvae (Vanderplancke et al., 2015), juveniles of *Scophthalmus maximus* (Pichavant et al., 2000, 2001), *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Pichavant et al., 2001) and *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Aksakal and Ekinci, 2021). Most of these studies propose that the reduction of growth and body condition under hypoxia are related to decreased food intake as well as decreased energy to process the food, a mechanism to offset the costs associated with growth when metabolism needs to slow down. Although food intake rates were not evaluated in our study, hypoxia alone did not induce stress in growth or body condition, suggesting that food intake and energy conversion were not affected by hypoxia. *A. presbyter* larvae can therefore invest energy in growth, in a similar way to those fish exposed to optimal conditions (Ern et al., 2016). On the other hand, exposure to hypoxia clearly induced stress on the aerobic metabolism, since RMR was reduced by about 60 % when compared to normoxic exposure. This decrease in MO_2 may be the result of a down-regulation protein turnover and/or a reduction in activity levels, as an energy conservation strategy (Pichavant et al., 2001; Richards, 2009). The literature is limited regarding the effects of hypoxia on fish early life stage metabolism. Lima et al. (2024a) did not find any evidence of metabolic depression in *Diplodus sargus* larvae exposed to hypoxic conditions for a two-week duration, which contrasts with our findings. However, other studies focusing on adult fish are consistent with the outcomes of the present study. Ern et al. (2016) found in *Cyclopterus*

lumpus and *Sciaenops ocellatus*, a decrease in RMR was observed with the decrease in water oxygen tension from 140 mmHg to values below 40 mmHg. Similar results were also observed in *Dicentrarchus labrax*, when subjected to O₂ saturation levels between 20 % and 30 %, and below 20 % (Claireaux and Lagardère, 1999). Richards (2009) and Mandic and Regan (2018) proposed that when O₂ availability is reduced, RMR can be maintained until a fish reaches its critical oxygen tension (Pcrit), after which they become dependent on environmental O₂ levels. Despite this, our results did not detect any change in fish fitness and mortality, and it is likely that although RMR is reduced under hypoxia, *A. presbyter* larvae may boost metabolic costs via another metabolic pathway, such as the anaerobic reliance (Lima et al., 2024a). Small pelagic fishes, for example, have evolved efficient anaerobic metabolism to support swimming performance (Killen et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2023). These results may suggest that O₂ levels between 2 and 2.5 mg L⁻¹ are not critical enough to potentially affect fitness and mortality of *A. presbyter* larvae, and therefore larvae have not yet reached Pcrit (Mandic and Regan, 2018). However, it is very likely that the reduction in RMR will affect the ability of *A. presbyter* to withstand thermal stress in warmer environments.

Our study corroborates the hypothesis proposed by Del Rio et al. (2019), who suggests that critical thermal tolerance (CTmax) is reduced when O₂ availability is low due to a deficiency of O₂ transport to tissues and impairment of metabolism (Richards, 2009; Wang et al., 2014; Islam et al., 2020). In line with this our findings indicate that hypoxia reduced the CTmax of *A. presbyter* larvae. Such negative relationship between O₂ availability and CTmax was also observed in adults of *Fundulus heteroclitus* exposed to anoxia (0.8 mg L⁻¹) (Healy and Schulte, 2012) and *Salvelinus fontinalis* exposed to acute hypoxia (2 mg L⁻¹) (Ellis et al., 2013). In *Cyclopterus lumpus* and *Sciaenops ocellatus* adults exposed to a wide range of O₂ concentrations, CTmax was only reduced when O₂ concentration was near Pcrit (Ern et al., 2016). Controversially, CTmax was independent of oxygen availability in *Oncorhynchus mykiss* adults after >3 months of exposure to O₂ concentrations of 40 % (Motyka et al., 2017). Considering this, Ern et al. (2016) proposed a new metric for analyzing the dependence of CTmax on oxygen, the partial pressure of O₂ at which CTmax changes from oxygen-independent to oxygen-dependent (Pctmax). Pctmax has never been evaluated in *A. presbyter*, however our study suggests that CTmax have already switched to the oxygen-dependent state at 2.5 mg L⁻¹ dissolved oxygen. Fish can respond to the effects of hypoxia on CTmax by increasing ventilation rates and increasing the number of erythrocytes, for better oxygen collection and transport to the tissues, however such mechanisms will involve high energy costs (Mandic and Regan, 2018). Larvae of *A. presbyter* may not be able to respond physiologically to the acute increase in temperature, at oxygen concentrations close to 2 mg L⁻¹, although they respond behaviorally to the acute increase in temperature by trying to capture air from the top layer of water.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the resilience of sand smelt larvae in the face of reduced O₂ availability, as evidenced by their capacity to sustain vital fitness-related traits, such as growth and overall condition. This resilience is likely achieved through a strategic investment in growth, akin to individuals in normoxic conditions. Results also suggest that the larvae have not yet reached Pcrit at 2.5 mg L⁻¹, even though metabolic depression is occurring as an attempt to conserve energy. This metabolic depression will allow them to extend their survival period with limited energy reserves. On the other hand, larvae are unable to respond physiologically to a sudden increase in temperature. These findings support the OCLTT hypothesis, suggesting that limited oxygen availability becomes a constraining factor for thermal tolerance. This limitation arises from the inability of respiratory and circulatory systems to effectively capture and transport O₂ to the tissues in quantities sufficient to meet energy demands. Future studies should evaluate the specific O₂

concentration at which Pcrit is reached and when CTmax transitions from oxygen-independent to oxygen-dependent. Additionally, it would be important to evaluate the synergistic effects of hypoxia with other environmental stressors, such as temperature, acidification, as well as food availability, which has been largely underexplored.

Overall, this work supports the evidence that hypoxia can reduce thermal tolerance, pointing out that *A. presbyter* larvae, although resilient to hypoxia events, are vulnerable to the joint action of reduced O₂ availability and acute temperature increase. This could be problematic in an era of climate change, where OMZ's and Marine Heat Waves are an increasingly frequent phenomena.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

João Almeida: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **André R.A. Lima:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Ana Margarida Faria:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ana Rita Lopes:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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